

Ethical Behavior of Senior Management and Its Impact on Enhancing Guest Satisfaction: A Case Study of the Opinions of a Sample of Managers of First-Class Hotels in the Holy City of Karbala

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Abstract

The research aims to know the nature of the relationship between the ethical behavior of senior management and guest satisfaction in first-class hotels in the holy city of Karbala, represented by the hotels (Baron, Hoda Al-Wali, Rotana Rayhaan Karbala and Damas), and based on the importance of the research topic in hotel organizations and the influence that these organizations have in society. The research problem was embodied in a central question: What is the effect of the ethical behavior of senior management in enhancing guest satisfaction in the hotels studied? The research adopted the descriptive analytical method in completing the research by collecting data. A questionnaire form was used to collect data that was distributed to a purposive sample of (80) Respondents were represented by (hotel managers and their assistants, department managers and their assistants, and front-line activity officials who have direct contact with the guests), and the research included two main hypotheses, which were subjected to appropriate statistical analysis. It was used in the (SPSS v23) statistical program for frequency distribution, graphical shapes, and percentages. Weighted arithmetic mean, standard deviation, relative importance (severity of answer), Spearman's rank correlation coefficient, simple Pearson correlation coefficient, simple linear regression coefficient, multiple regression coefficients, coefficient of determination R^2 , F test (F-test), sequential regression test, Which gave numerical results, a set of recommendations were arranged, the most important of which was to enhance the ethical behaviors of the senior administrative leadership in hotel organizations by activating the activities and capabilities available to hold training courses, seminars, and workshops to instill moral values and effective behavior in them to enhance guest satisfaction.

Keywords: Ethical Behavior, Guest Satisfaction, Hotels

Introduction

Morality is one of the most important meanings of life and an essential element for the existence and survival of society, as no association can continue and flourish if it is not governed by a set of rules and regulations that regulate the relationships of individuals and groups among themselves, and work to guide their morals and behavior, and this is what all religions seek. Heavenly

organizations, tourism, and community organizations, and paying attention to ethical conduct in hotel organizations are an effective means of developing the moral awareness of senior management to ensure that appropriate decisions are made and contribute to reactions to unethical behavior in the manner preferred by the recipient and to bear risks and continue updating work systems by the surrounding variables that affect the image. It is inevitable in the success of the organization and achieving its goals, which will represent an additional opportunity to enhance the positive feeling generated by the guest when his desires are satisfied and his needs for services or products are met and compared to what he would have received when trying the same services or products from competitors, and thus gaining his satisfaction, as it is not possible to imagine the success of the organization. Hotel services without achieving guest satisfaction are essential for retaining them for the most extended period. Based on the study of the relationship between the ethical behavior of senior management and guest satisfaction, the concept and importance will be addressed. The dimensions of ethical conduct of senior management will be identified, and the most prominent methods of measuring guest satisfaction will lead to testing the study's hypotheses and identifying the nature of the relationship.

Chapter One Methodology

First, The research problem: Today's society faces large and complex issues about optimal ethical dealings among its components. Hence, the research problem arises in choosing a variety of ethical behaviors for its members to ensure the existence of high-quality ethical dealings, whether these dealings are internal among the elements of the hotel organization or External between the organization and the guest. Therefore, the research problem can be formulated with a general question: (Does the ethical behavior of senior management impact guest satisfaction in the hotels studied)? Sub-questions emerge from it, which are as follows:

1. What is the level of ethical behavior of senior management in the hotels studied?
2. What is the level of guest satisfaction in the hotels studied?
3. What is the correlation between ethical behavior and guest satisfaction in the hotels studied?
4. What is the level and direction of the influence relationship between ethical behavior and guest satisfaction in the hotels studied?

Second: The importance of the research: The importance of the study is represented in the following:

1. Increasing interest in monitoring, analyzing, and interpreting the most precise aspects related to the administrative systems of hotel organizations.
2. Providing researchers with numerical indications of the relationship between the ethical behavior of senior management and achieving guest satisfaction.
3. Highlighting the importance of research variables for developing hotel organizations.
4. Diagnosing the state of ethical behavior of senior management and guest satisfaction in the sample studied.

Third: Research objectives: The research aims to:

1. Unify cognitive efforts regarding the intellectual accumulation of ethical behavior and guest satisfaction.

2. Explain the importance of the research variables to senior management and workers in the hotel organizations under research.
3. Determine the reality of thinking adopted by the senior management in the investigated hotels.
4. Forming a future vision of the reality of guest satisfaction when there is ethical behavior by senior management in the investigated hotels.

Chapter Two

The first axis: Research Methodology

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Fourth: Hypothetical research model

A hypothetical research model was designed as in Figure (1), which indicates (the correlation and influence relationship) between the dimensions of ethical behavior and guest satisfaction.

Figure (1): The hypothetical search chart.

Fifth: Research Hypotheses:

The first primary hypothesis: There is a statistically significant correlation between the ethical behavior of senior management and guest satisfaction.

The second primary hypothesis: There is a statistically significant effect of the ethical behavior of senior management on guest satisfaction.

Sixth: Research Methodology: The descriptive analytical method was adopted to identify the reality of the research variables and place them in their appropriate context. This helps reach the research results and formulate solutions through recommendations and proposals.

Seventh: Limits of research:

1. Time limits: The research period was limited to the period (11/21/2023-10/1/2023).
2. Spatial boundaries: First-class hotels in the holy city of Karbala, were chosen as a site for conducting the applied study.
3. Human limits: The research was limited to a group of managers of first-class hotels in the holy city of Karbala.

Eighth: Methods of collecting data: The research relied on both theoretical and applied aspects of several tools, including:

1. The theoretical aspect: Arab and foreign sources were used, in addition to periodicals, magazines, research, theses, university dissertations, and the international information network (the Internet), which are related to the research topic, to cover the theoretical aspect of the research and support the field aspect with it.

2. The applied aspect: A questionnaire was developed to collect information from primary sources.

Ninth: Statistical methods used to measure and analyze the research variables: The following methods were adopted:

A - Frequency and percentages: to analyze the answers of sample members.

B- The (weighted) arithmetic mean is one of the measures of central tendency.

T - Standard deviation, used to determine the extent of the dispersion of respondents' opinions.

D- Coefficient of variation, used to determine the fluctuation of the arithmetic mean values.

C- The simple correlation coefficient to determine the type of relationship between the research variables.

H- Simple linear regression.

X- Multiple regression coefficients.

D- Coefficient of determination R^2 .

Y- Test (sequential regression).

T- Graphical figures.

The second axis (theoretical aspect).

Some common concepts and terms included in this research were summarized: the idea, importance, and dimensions of ethical behavior for senior management, the concept, volume, and most prominent methods of measuring guest satisfaction.

First: Ethical behavior of senior management:

1. The concept of ethical behavior: Ethical behavior is affected by several negative and positive influences, internal and external, and business organizations are affected by the prevailing laws, legislation, values, and customs, and therefore, in their entirety, they give an idea about the nature of the prevailing ethical climate and in turn move the ethical behavior of individuals. Starks & Anderson (2012:37) defined it as adherence to the values and traditions prevailing in society and an attempt to behave

In a socially and ethically acceptable manner. (Wheelen & Hunger, 2012, 88) Indicated that it is a set of agreed-upon opinions regarding acceptable standards of behavior in the commercial or craft profession. (David & Mayer, 2010:2) viewed it as individual behavior that is subject to or judged according to generally accepted standards of ethical behavior. Bishop, 2013:657 stated that it is a collective thought process related to the ethical behavior of individuals. (Daft, 2015:390) added that it combines cultural, societal, and familial backgrounds and influences. Hassanian & Shayan, 2017:3) emphasized that it is both desirable behavior. It introduces various moral behaviors to achieve moral virtues related to the self. Recognizing human aspects and promoting human dignity rather than diverse cultures is important.

As for the concept of senior management, which is the engine of tourism organizations, the organizations' paths are determined by the general vision they adopt and the decisions they take and are based on. The scientist Frederick Taylor referred to it as the correct and accurate knowledge of what individuals are intended to perform, then ensuring that they serve it in the best and least expensive way (Hassan and Al-Ajami, 2010: 28). Therefore, senior management in tourism organizations should adopt ethical behaviors that improve employee morale by providing various forms of psychological support. Through the several definitions mentioned that show the concept of ethical behavior, we can develop a procedural description of ethical behavior, explaining that it is a set of principles, rules, and standards that dictate the correct behavior of the senior management in the tourism organization.

2 . The importance of ethical behavior for senior management in tourism organizations:

Ethical behavior is the path that hotel organizations take to move forward in their activities, paying high attention to everything related to moral obligations that are of great importance to guests, who in turn distinguish organizations that achieve better ethical standards in their business activity. To achieve economic interests, no matter who their owners are, their influence, and their ranks, success and excellence cannot be conducted at the expense of the fundamental rights and freedoms of the individual. Rather, rights have priority in work, and most declared morals are subject to the nature of the work and activity that individuals carry out. And groups,

each according to its specialization, that tourism work has its specificity related to its core and making the optimal decision from a legal and ethical standpoint, taking into account that its decision is made with integrity and conviction and does not harm any other person (Al-Houri, 2004: 95). It may be in the interest of the hotel management or tourism organization. Establishing unique professional controls and ethics with the aim of controlling the behavior of employees and holding them accountable when they violate them and for the purpose of regulating the relationship between employees and guests in order to provide high-quality services, the most important of which are: that the guest is always right while respecting and adhering to the rules and regulations of the hotel, having high morals and providing the required service in Standard time and constant commitment to calm and reassurance and providing assistance to the guest with all politeness and respect (Lesley & Richard, 2005:33). There is also a set of ethical principles related to travelers that reflect some ethical behaviors in dealing with residents and protecting cultural heritage in order to activate human and social relations on The basis of mutual respect and building essential bridges in dealing with others in the host country, and that ties be friendly and good, away from distress and tension with others (Medlike, 2003: 64).

3. Several researchers have researched some aspects of senior management's ethical behavior, but the specific aspects have varied according to the research's context and the sample used. This led to the selection of characteristics that align with the reality of the studied hotel organizations. What's more, the majority of the researchers also agreed on these dimensions. (Rest, 1986:556, Jones, 1996:37) as a foundation and based on the following:-

A - Conscience of tourists: It establishes if people can find moral reasoning in other people's actions and whether they can also identify immorality (Barnes & Wagner, 2015: 182). Being morally conscious is the initial stage in making an ethical choice, and it is also an essential component of general moral behavior and many other parts of life (Lin & Zhang, 2011:145). It allows the person in charge to admit when anything is causing him to feel uncomfortable ethically. Considering the matter from an ethical standpoint within the tourism industry would help him understand the significance of moral awareness; otherwise, those in positions of power will be blind to the fact that their actions have ethical consequences (Trevino & Nelson, 2011: 71). As we can see, moral awareness in the tourist industry refers to top-level management's understanding of how their decisions affect other people.

Section B, "Ethical Decisions in Tourism," describes how industry executives weigh the pros and cons of doing the right thing against what is considered socially acceptable (Gibbs, 2010:52). It was described by Emery (2016:5) as a positional decision choice, or judgment reached after much deliberation. Executives' capacity and efficiency in making the proper ethical judgment is critical to the hotel organization's performance, and the decision-making process is central to the administrative process. Their decision-making responsibilities include almost every facet of the administrative organization; decision-making is an integral aspect of management, which is one of the roles of senior management.

The second is visitor satisfaction, crucial for tourist organizations to keep their guests returning. Since the guest is central to its operations and very being, this section will shed light on the most critical aspects of it, the most common ways to quantify it, and the perspectives of scholars who have attempted to address these issues:

1. The idea of making guests happy: The theories and philosophies of scholars in administration and tourism led to many suggestions for improving the tourist experience. According to Monin (2001:108), it is the guest's perception of how well services and activities meet his requirements and expectations. The customer's level of satisfaction (or lack thereof) is based on how well the product meets his needs and expectations, as highlighted by Anis (2016:14). Regarding this, Wei (2020:10) also described it as an emotion that arises when the product's actual performance falls short of the customer's expectations. As a result of his purchases or his impressions of different parts of the tourist program, the customer could have a good or bad response (Kotler, 2006:172). In addition, as Al-Afandi (2018:43) points out, it evaluates the degree to which the actualization of guests' wants and requirements surpasses their expectations. Establishing strong ties with the beneficiaries is crucial for this to be accomplished. According to Kotler (2018:343), it's the customer's evaluation based on his expectations for the product and how well it works. The organization may attain visitor satisfaction and loyalty by providing the most significant goods and services at the proper time and price (Qammach & Al-Sharifi, 2021:5216).

The researcher constructs the following procedural idea based on the identified concepts for visitor satisfaction: Customer satisfaction is the degree to which a service meets or exceeds the expectations of its target audience in meeting their requirements and wants.

2. Reasons why tourist organization cares so much about happy customers (Kotler & Armstrong, 2000:58), (Zulficar & Shafaat, 2015:115), (Olsen, 2017:4), ((Yusof et al., 2017:1), (Barlan)) all provide definitions of the significance of visitor pleasure. (Vafaei et al., 2019:477), (Espino, 2017:123).

a. Raising customer devotion to the brand's offerings.

B. The level of service is determined by how satisfied the guests are.

C. If any rules are in place that might damage guests' experience, reevaluate them and remove them.

Dr. It raises the organization's profile, which brings in more customers.

H. Customers are less likely to go with other businesses in the market.

Moreover, the. Our efforts are paying off, and the company will have a leg up in the market in the long run.

g. Efficiently and effectively meet visitors' demands and increase their satisfaction while implementing methods that alleviate environmental deterioration to benefit society and the environment.

H. It aids the company in assessing its service delivery performance and the abilities of its executives and staff.

I. A significant boost in income is possible by drastically lowering the visitor loss rate.

Yes. If his expectations are met, he will be satisfied, and if he is confident to an appropriate degree, he will be very loyal to the company.

K. Based on visitors' thoughts, which include feedback, create a strategy for allocating resources so that they may fulfill their objectives and achieve their goals.

Thus, hotel organizations strive to deliver top-notch services with the visitor as their primary focus. The client's pleasure is crucial to the organization's viability, ensuring its duties are met and serving as its *raison d'être*. Consequently, the company should be aware of its goals and requirements.

3. Factors contributing to satisfied guests: Developing a method to assess and monitor guest satisfaction properly and continually is crucial since various internal and external elements impact it. If this doesn't happen, the organization can only accomplish its short-term objectives. Critical measuring techniques that apply to the present study include: - a. Complaints and Suggestions Systems: These can be anything from the satisfaction surveys that some businesses give their customers to online feedback forms that allow customers to voice their opinions about a product or service to more traditional methods of contact like phone calls, email, or even paper forms. Many smart people work for businesses, which allows them to act swiftly when issues arise (Chait, 2015:255).

B. Surveys for Guest Satisfaction: By periodically surveying, sending questionnaires, or calling a random sample of present visitors, responding organizations may get direct measurements of guest satisfaction. Data on customer satisfaction may be supplemented with questions designed to gauge repurchase intent, allowing them to gain insight into how customers see rival offerings (Kotler & Armstrong, 2000:43).

Part Two: The Real World

Greetings and salutations! We posed the research hypotheses as questions to ensure the reliability of the study plan's hypothetical connections. To verify the assumptions, the sample was selected from the research community, which includes managers of first-class hotels in the sacred city of Karbala. Data collection and analysis techniques for... The following paragraphs will explain the realities of these hotels:

First, the site where the study will be conducted: The research and its variables were tested using authorized criterion items at hotels in the sacred city of Karbala.

Secondly, the study's participants and samples: Managers of five-star hotels in the sacred city of Karbala make up the study population. A total of sixty questionnaires were sent out to the participants in the study. Once they were marked, they were collected and prepared for the research.

Thirdly, data collection instruments:

Survey No. 1: Within the context of the selected topic, a series of related questions was identified to accomplish the study objective. The study variables were measured using a questionnaire to gather data for analysis. The questionnaire was produced according to the research's needs and trends and followed a set of criteria to ensure accuracy. For this reason, the pentagonal scale was chosen, as seen in the accompanying document.

Questionnaire description: This questionnaire was designed to measure and analyze questions and hypotheses about the ethical behavior of senior management in first-class hotels in Karbala. It also measured the extent to which these hotels included and were able to enhance guest satisfaction. The questionnaire was divided into sections according to the research variables on the theoretical side.

The initial part of the survey asks identifying questions about the participants, including their gender, age, level of education, length of employment, and amount of training.

- The following part: It has fourteen paragraphs that describe the independent variable, which is the ethical conduct of upper-level management, and it has two dimensions, with seven sections each for ethical awareness and moral decision-making.

The third portion is divided into two parts, with six paragraphs each, and it describes the dependent variable, which is improving guests' contentment. This dependent variable is spread across two dimensions: the complaints system and guest satisfaction surveys. We will use SPSS v23 to assess the validity and reliability of all twenty-six items.

Research variables and their sub-dimensions are shown in Table (1).

Number Of Paragraphs	Search Variables	
7	Moral Awareness	X1
7	Ethical Decision Making	X2
14	Ethical Behavior Of Senior Management	X
6	Complaints System	Y1
6	Guest Satisfaction Surveys	Y2
12	Enhance Guest Satisfaction	Y
26	All Items Of The Questionnaire	

Data description and analysis methods: SPSS v23 tests hypotheses about the study's problems and answers its questions. Among these methods are graphical representations of the data, percentages, weighted arithmetic mean, standard deviation, relative importance (severity of answer), multiple regression coefficients, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient, simple Pearson correlation coefficient, simple linear regression coefficient, multiple regression, coefficient of determination R², F test (F-test), and sequential regression testing.

Table (2) Correlation coefficient values

Interpretation	Correlation Coefficient Value
Perfect Connection	$r = 1$
Strong Connection	$0.5 \leq r < 1$
Average Correlation	$0.3 \leq r < 0.5$
Weak Connection	$0 < r < 0.3$
There Is No Connection	$r = 0$

Fourth: Testing honesty and reliability.

1. Ensuring the questionnaire's apparent validity: This refers to the questionnaire's capacity to convey its intended purpose, to measure the intended constructs, to reflect the content to be weighted, and to measure the intended constructs of the research. Among these options, the most straightforward is relying on the integrity of the arbitrators with expertise in the relevant field; this particular case was brought to many arbitrators. We revised and edited a few lines after considering how they relate to the dimension we're measuring.

2. The reliability of the survey: When used repeatedly, the instruments and measurements provide consistent, favorable findings. The findings are compatible if the researcher measures again. Repeated testing of the same study sample at various intervals guarantees that these estimations

are stable. We have completed this. The dependability is determined by using the Alpha-Cornbach coefficient technique. We utilize this coefficient to determine how regular the estimations that we get from tests or questionnaires that assess a topic whose items are believed to be homogenous. This approach relies on the (Cronbach Alpha) equation for reliability extraction. Alpha-Cornbach). To consider the questionnaire reliable and distribute it to the complete sample, the reliability coefficient value has to be higher than (0.60).

Table (3): Reliability coefficient values and interpretation of their significance

Interpretation	Stability Coefficient Value
Excellent Stability	0.90 – or more
Very Good Stability	0.89 – 0.80
Good Stability (This Is What Is Achieved In Most Tests)	0.79 – 0.70
Low Stability (Needs Review)	0.69–0.50
Poor Reliability (The Test Does Not Contribute To The Relationship)	0.49 or less

Source: Gouda, Mahfouz (2010), p. 25.

If the reliability coefficient is (0.70) or more, this is appropriate for research and studies in which the questionnaire is an approved tool. The two methods were applied to the research forms, and the results are in Table (4) as follows:

Table (4): Reliability Test Results

Interpretation	The value of Cronbach's alpha coefficient Cornbach,s Alpha	Search Variables	
(Passes the test) There is stability in the items of the first dimension	0.870	Moral Awareness	X1
(Passes the test) There is stability in the things of the second dimension	0.758	Ethical Decision Making	X2
(Passes the test) The presence of peace in the independent variable items	0.908	Ethical Behavior of Senior Management	X
(It passes the test) There is stability in the things of the first dimension	0.909	Complaints System	Y1

It passes the test for peace in the things of the second dimension	0.902	Guest Satisfaction Surveys	Y2
It passes the test for peace in the dependent variable items	0.949	Enhance Guest Satisfaction	Y
(Passes the test) There is consistency in all the questionnaire items	0.959	All Items Of The Questionnaire	

Source: Prepared by the researcher according to the results of the SPSS V23 program.

Fifth: Descriptive analysis of the individuals in the research sample:

Table (5) shows the identifying information of the individuals in the surveyed sample, which included variables (gender, age, educational qualification, years of work, number of training courses), which we summarize as follows:

Table (5): Description of the Research Sample Member.

The Ratio	The Number	Target Groups	Variables
%70	42	Male	Gender
%30	18	Female	
100%	60	The Total	
21.7%	13	Less than 30 years old	Age
36.7%	22	31-40 years old	
26.6%	16	41-50 years old	
15 %	9	51 years and over	
% 100	60	The Total	
23.3%	14	Diploma or less	Qualification
41.7%	25	Bachelor's	
15 %	9	Master's	
20 %	12	Ph.D.	
100 %	60	The Total	
30 %	18	Less than 5 years	Years of work
40 %	24	5 - 10 years	
16.7%	10	11-15 years	
13.3%	8	16 years and over	
100 %	60	The Total	
6.7 %	4	I did not participate	Number of training courses
31.7 %	19	One course	
20 %	12	Two courses	

41.6 %	25	Three or more courses	
100 %	60	The Total	

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the results of the SPSS V23 program

The chart above shows that a large majority of the sample members have high levels of education, with many having completed more than three courses. This helps to ensure that the sample members' responses are realistic and scientific.

Sixth: The significance of the study's factors (improving guests' happiness and ethical conduct by upper management):- A

Tables displaying trends in the sample's responses for each paragraph illustrate the contents of the questionnaire questions about the independent variable (the two-dimensional ethical behavior of senior management) and the dependent variable (the two-dimensional enhancement of guest satisfaction). The sample consisted of sixty individuals, and this paragraph pertains to their responses. Answer strength matrices, standard deviations, and arithmetic means were used.

Table (6): Estimated scale according to a five-point Likert scale

The Level	Weighted average	Complaints System
Low	From 1 to 1.79	Strongly Disagree
	From 1.80 to 2.59	Disagree
Middle	From 2.60 to 3.39	Neutral
High	From 3.40 to 4.19	Agree
	From 4.2 to 5	Strongly Agree

Source: (Barakat: 2013:P13)

1. The moral actions of upper-level executives: The research questionnaire had fourteen questions spread out over two dimensions, with the overarching goal of gauging the level of access that senior management at first-class hotels have to the tools they need to act ethically; the results showed that These are the axes that make up the sample: a. A sense of right and wrong: The study sample did not agree on most paragraphs of this axis, since the arithmetic mean for this axis was (3.81), which lies within the period (3.40 to 4.19). The relative significance value reached (76.13%), a small proportion that validates this. Table (7) and Figure (2) show that the sample's answers are biased towards agreement and have a standard deviation of 1.31, which shows how homogeneous the responses are concerning moral awareness.

Table (7): Description of the sample's responses to the items of the first dimension (ethical awareness) of the ethical behavior variable for senior management

Relative importance	deviation Standard	Arithmetic mean	Paragraphs										Dimensions	
			5		4		3		2		1			
			Sample answers and percentages											
			%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f		
72.00	1.330	3.60	28.3	17	36.7	22	15	9	6.7	4	13.3	8	Q1	X1 Moral awarene
73.66	1.308	3.68	30	18	40	24	10	6	8.3	5	11.7	7	Q2	

74.3 4	1.342	3.7 2	38. 3	23	26. 7	16	11.7	7	15	9	8. 3	5	Q3
73.6 0	1.372	3.6 8	38. 3	23	25	15	13. 3	8	13. 3	8	10	6	Q4
80.6 6	1.353	4.0 3	55	33	20	12	8.3	5	6.7	4	10	6	Q5
81.0 2	1.268	4.0 5	51. 7	31	23. 3	14	11.7	7	5	3	8. 3	5	Q6
77.6 6	1.195	3.8 8	40	24	28. 3	17	16. 7	1 0	10	6	5	3	Q7
76.13		1.31	3.81	Total									

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the results of the SPSS V23 program.

Following the section on moral awareness, the importance of the following paragraphs was distributed as follows: quarter (Q6) received the highest level of response, with an arithmetic mean value of (4.05) and a standard deviation of (1.268), and its relative importance constituted (81.02%), indicating that the majority of the research sample agreed with this paragraph. According to the statement, "that senior management presents new ideas to develop work automatically and quickly," the item measuring moral awareness with the lowest response level was paragraph Q1, with an arithmetic mean score of 3.60. Confirming that some study sample members agreed on (the competence of top management to recognize ethical viewpoints), the standard deviation was reported at 1.330, and the relative significance was 72.00%.

Figure (2): The relative importance of the sample's answers regarding agreement on the items of the first dimension (ethical awareness) of the ethical behavior variable of senior management

A. Moral judgments: With an arithmetic mean for this axis of 3.72 (ranging from 3.40 to 4.19), the relative significance value reached 74.54%, a respectable number that verifies the study sample's agreement on the majority of paragraphs along this axis. Table (8) and Figure (3) show that the sample's responses are pretty homogeneous concerning (ethical decision-making), with a standard deviation of 1.23. This suggests that the answers are moving in the direction of agreement.

Table (8): Description of the sample's responses to the items of the second dimension (ethical decision making) for the ethical behavior variable of senior management

Relative importance	deviation Standard	Arithmetic mean	Paragraphs										Dimensions	
			5		4		3		2		1			
			Sample answers and percentages											
			%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f		
83.66	1.228	4.18	60	36	18.3	11	6.7	4	10	6	5	3	Q8	X2 Moral awareness
75.02	1.361	3.75	41.7	25	23.3	14	11.7	7	15	9	8.3	5	Q9	
79.74	1.049	3.98	31.7	19	51.7	31	5	3	6.7	4	5	3	Q10	
72.66	1.262	3.63	26.7	16	38.3	23	18.3	11	5	3	11.7	7	Q11	
67.00	1.147	3.35	21.7	13	18.3	11	38.3	23	16.7	10	5	3	Q12	
62.00	1.231	3.10	15	9	20	12	40	24	10	6	15	9	Q13	
81.68	1.331	4.08	56.7	34	20	12	8.3	5	5	3	10	6	Q14	
74.54	1.23	3.72	Total											

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the results of the SPSS V23 program

Paragraph (Q8) received the highest proportion of points after (making an ethical decision), with an arithmetic mean of (4.18), a standard deviation of (1.228), and relative importance of (83.66%), indicating that the majority of the research sample agreed with this paragraph. Before making ethical judgments, all relevant data should be thoroughly gathered and organized. Additionally, with an arithmetic mean value of 3.10 and a standard deviation of 1.231, paragraph Q13) had the fewest responses out of all the paragraphs dealing with ethical decision-making. Confirming (62.0%) that study participants needed to be more specific (that senior management looks for someone else to blame when they mess up and face delicate ethical issues head-on) was the relative significance.

Figure (3): The relative importance of the sample's answers regarding agreement on the items of the second dimension (Ethical decision making) for the variable of ethical behavior of senior management)

Table 9 shows that the variable (senior management's ethical behavior) had a weighted arithmetic mean value of 3.77, falling from 3.40 to 4.19. A standard deviation of 1.27 shows how homogeneous the replies of the study sample are concerning this variable; this suggests that the sample's answers tend towards agreement. Consistent with the study sample's consensus on most paragraphs (senior management's ethical conduct), the relative significance was also measured at 75.34 percent.

Table (9): Level of importance of the independent variable, ethical behavior of senior management

Ranking	Level of Response of Sample Members	Relative Importance	Standard Deviation	Weighted Arithmetic Average	Variables	Code
The First	Good	76.13	1.31	3.81	Moral Awareness	X1
The Second	Good	74.54	1.23	3.72	Ethical Decision Making	X2
The Independent	Good	75.34	1.27	3.77	Ethical Behavior of Senior Management	X

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the results of the SPSS V23 program.

To compare the axes (ethical behavior of senior management) in terms of relative importance, it is noted that the axis (moral awareness) obtained the highest level of relative importance at (76.13%), and (ethical decision-making) recorded the lowest level at (74.54%), as shown in the figure. (4).

Figure (4): shows the relative importance of the ethical behavior axes of senior management

The research sample's highest percentage of correct responses was for (ethical awareness), which suggests that (senior management's attention or knowledge of the impact of its actions on

other individuals) is essential, followed by (decision-making) according to the level of importance, arithmetic mean, and standard deviation of the independent variable (ethical behavior). Identifying what constitutes morally acceptable and incorrect conduct about specific tasks is an ethical consideration.

1. Raising levels of visitor contentment: To determine the level of guest satisfaction in the studied hotels, a research questionnaire was used. The questionnaire consisted of twelve questions spread out over two dimensions. The results of the sample's responses to the satisfaction axes were as follows:

a. A method for grievances: As the arithmetic mean for this axis was recorded at 3.66, which falls within the period (3.40 to 4.19), the value of relative significance reached 72.42%, which is a solid proportion that reflects the agreement of the study sample on most of the paragraphs. This indicates a trend towards understanding in the sample's responses. As shown in Table (10), the level of homogeneity of the replies about the complaints system is indicated by a standard deviation of 1.29.

Table (10): Description of the sample's answers to the paragraphs of the first dimension (complaints system) to enhance guest satisfaction

Relative importance	standard deviation	Arithmetic mean	Paragraphs										Dimensions			
			5		4		3		2		1					
			Sample answers and percentages													
			%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f				
73.98	1.239	3.70	28.3	17	40	24	15	9	6.7	4	10	6	Q15	Complaints system		
63.88	1.110	3.43	20	12	26.7	16	35	21	1.3	8	5	3	Q16			
68.28	1.369	3.42	25	15	33.3	20	13.3	8	15	9	13.3	8	Q17			
79.32	1.262	3.97	50	30	18.3	11	15	9	11.7	7	5	3	Q18			
74.36	1.485	3.72	45	27	21.7	13	6.7	4	13.3	8	13.3	8	Q19			
74.68	1.260	3.73	31.7	19	38.3	23	10	6	11.7	7	8.3	5	Q20			
72.42	1.29	3.66	Total													

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the results of the SPSS V23 program

With a relative importance of (79.32%) and an arithmetic mean of (3.97) and a standard deviation of (1.262), the highest level of response achieved by paragraph (Q18)—which relates to the complaints system—was distributed among the subsequent paragraphs' importance levels. This confirms that all members of the research sample agreed with this paragraph. This indicates that (the hotels' upper management will keep providing excellent service no matter what) to keep

guests happy. Paragraph Q16) also had the fewest responses out of all the paragraphs in the complaints system, with an arithmetic mean of 3.43 and a standard deviation of 1.110. Furthermore, the proportion of (63.88%), which validates the consensus among the study's participants, states that (the administration offers a complaints box with other privacy protection measures).

Figure (5): The relative importance of the sample's answers regarding agreement on the items of the first dimension

Complaints system to enhance guest satisfaction.

A. Polls to gauge satisfied customers: An encouraging 73.53% relative significance rating indicates that the study sample agrees with most of the paragraphs along this axis. Within the range of (3.40 to 4.19), the geometric mean for this axis was (3.67). Table (11) implies that the majority of the sample is in agreement, and the slight standard deviation of 1.30 shows how homogeneous the solutions are with respect to the (guest satisfaction surveys).

Table (11): Description of the sample's answers to the items of the second dimension (guest satisfaction surveys) to enhance guest satisfaction

Relative importance	standard deviation	Arithmetic mean	Paragraphs										Dimensions	
			5		4		3		2		1			
			Sample answers and percentages											
			%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f		
79.06	1.346	3.95	50	30	21.7	13	11.7	7	6.7	4	10	6	Q21	Y2 Guest satisfaction surveys
85.00	1.202	4.25	63.3	38	16.7	10	6.7	4	8.3	5	5	3	Q22	
67.74	1.329	3.38	21.7	13	36.7	22	11.7	7	18.3	11	11.7	7	Q23	
67.74	1.329	3.38	21.7	13	36.7	22	11.7	7	18.3	11	11.7	7	Q24	
79.98	1.390	4.00	55	33	18.3	11	10	6	5	3	11.7	7	Q25	
61.64	1.225	3.08	13.3	8	23.3	14	36.7	22	11.7	7	15	9	Q26	
73.53	1.30	3.67	Total											

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the results of the SPSS V23 program

The paragraphs that followed the guest satisfaction surveys were ranked according to their level of importance. Paragraph (Q22) received the highest level of response, with an arithmetic mean of 4.25 and a standard deviation of 1.202. Its relative importance constituted 85.00%, indicating that most of the research sample agreed with this paragraph. This suggests that (high-ranking hotel officials engage in two-way conversations with customers to gauge satisfaction with the establishment's offerings). Compared to the other sections in the guest satisfaction questionnaires, paragraph (Q26) had the lowest response level, with an arithmetic mean of 3.08 and a standard deviation of 3.08. The study sample members needed to be more confident that the administration employs workers as consumers of services in the rival organization to examine its services, as noted (1.225), and its relative significance was (61.64%).

Figure (6): The relative importance of the sample's answers regarding agreement on the items of the second dimension (guest satisfaction surveys) to enhance guest satisfaction.

Table (12) shows that the weighted arithmetic mean for the variable (increasing guest pleasure) was 3.67, within the range of 3.40 to 4.19. With a standard deviation of 1.30, which shows how homogeneous the responses are, the sample is trending toward agreement. A respectable proportion (72.98%) indicating agreement on the paragraphs (increasing visitor pleasure) was obtained in the replies of the study sample for this dimension, indicating its relative relevance.

Table (12): Level of importance of the dependent variable enhancing guest satisfaction

Ranking	Level of Response of Sample Members	Relative Importance	Standard Deviation	Weighted Arithmetic Average	Variables	Code
The Second	Good	72.42	1.29	3.66	Complaints System	Y1
The First	Good	73.53	1.3	3.67	Guest Satisfaction	Y2

					Surveys	
Follower	Good	72.98	1.30	3.67	Enhance Guest Satisfaction	Y

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the results of the SPSS V23 program.

To compare the axes of (enhancing guest satisfaction) in terms of relative importance, it is noted that the axis (guest satisfaction surveys) obtained the highest level of relative importance at (73.53%), and the axis (complaints system) recorded the lowest level at (72.42%), as shown in Figure (7).

Figure (7): Shows the relative importance of the axes of enhancing guest satisfaction

The research sample's most common response was for "guest satisfaction surveys," meaning measuring direct measures of guest satisfaction through conducting opinion polls occasionally is essential. The second most common response was for "the complaints system," which means that the organization's communication with its guests to know their grievances, suggestions, and complaints is essential.

Seventh, verifying the study's assumptions: We calculated the simple correlation coefficient (Pearson) to understand the interrelationships between the research variables using the simple linear regression model and the sequential multiple regression model. We then tested the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable and determined the significance of that effect using the F-test. The dependent variable's coefficient of determination (R²) was used to ascertain how much the independent variable impacted and contributed to the dependent variable.

The research hypotheses will be tested through the following paragraphs:

1. Testing the correlation and effect hypotheses:

We extended the correlation coefficient between them to determine whether a connection between the two variables supports the hypothesis. This allowed us to see how strongly and in what direction the two variables were related. Based on the results of the statistical analysis program v23 SPSS, we can confirm that there is a significant correlation between the two variables at a significance level of (0.01) or (0.05), respectively, if the correlation coefficient is limited to (0.50) or (1). To find out how much of an impact the independent variable (ethical behavior) had, we used the F-test. A significant effect is present in the dependent variable (improving guest satisfaction) for senior management if the probability value (Sig) is less than the significance threshold of (0.05), and the converse is also true.

Given that the computed value of (F) has more significance than its actual value, the probability tabulation suggests a statistically significant result, and the opposite is also true. Another statistic that was retrieved was the value of the coefficient of determination (R^2), which reveals the proportion of the interpretation (the ethical behavior of senior management) that was satisfied by the variable (improving guest satisfaction). This paragraph will conduct the testing of the following hypotheses:

The First Primary Hypothesis

(We find that senior management's ethical behavior correlates with increased visitor satisfaction, and this leads us to the following secondary hypotheses:)

- A person's level of moral awareness is significantly correlated with the complaints system.
- The complaints system is significantly correlated with ethical decision-making.
- Ethical awareness and surveys measuring customer satisfaction are significantly correlated.
- Guests are more likely to be satisfied when staff make ethical decisions, according to polls.
- Making ethical decisions has a statistically significant association with increasing visitor pleasure.
- Being ethically conscious has a statistically significant correlation with increasing guest satisfaction.

An Additional Central Theory:

(The ethical actions of upper-level management have a statistically significant impact on increasing visitor pleasure.) From these, the following secondary hypotheses are derived:

- The complaints system is significantly impacted by moral awareness.
- Ethical decision-making is significantly affected by the complaints system.
- Ethical awareness has a noticeable impact on visitor satisfaction surveys.
- Ethical decision-making has a noticeable impact on visitor satisfaction ratings.
- Making ethical decisions has a statistically significant impact on visitor satisfaction.
- Being ethically conscious has a statistically significant influence on guest satisfaction.

The following are the outcomes of the tests for association and influence between them, as shown in Table (13):

According to the first significant hypothesis, the complaints system correlates significantly with moral awareness. With a recorded value of 0.87 for the correlation coefficient, the first secondary hypothesis accepts this observation with a 95% confidence level. Conclusions drawn from the study's statistically significant sample support the idea that moral awareness is associated with the complaints system.

We can accept the first two secondary hypotheses from the second fundamental hypothesis, which states that the two variables are related. The estimated value of F, 173.802, demonstrated a statistically significant influence of the moral awareness variable on the complaints system. The result was the value of the coefficient of determination being recorded. (0.75%), the quantity representing the influence and contribution of (moral awareness) to (the complaints system).

a. The second of the two secondary hypotheses that follow the first core hypothesis—that there is a morally relevant association between the complaints system and ethical decision-making—is accepted with a 95% confidence level. This link—criticisms based on the opinions of the study's participants—was confirmed by the correlation coefficient, which was 0.69.

The estimated value of F, which was 53.433, demonstrated that the ethical decision-making variable had a statistically significant effect on the complaints system. As a result, we must accept the null hypothesis (that the two variables are unrelated) as accurately as the alternative (that they are connected) that follows from the first. What came out of it was the coefficient's recorded value. The influence and contribution of ethical decision-making to the complaints system is 0.48%.

B. A 95% confidence level was used to reject the third hypothesis derived from the first core hypothesis. We can rule out a high association between moral awareness and guest satisfaction surveys since the correlation coefficient of 0.002 confirms that there is just a weak link. The viewpoints expressed by the study's sample determine the interviewee's selection.

Because the estimated F value was 0.000, which is not statistically significant, we may conclude that moral awareness does not affect the dependent variable (guest satisfaction surveys). Consequently, the effect was recorded, and the third hypothesis that originated from the second basic assumption—that the two variables interact—was rejected. The significance of the coefficient of determination (0.000%) in guest satisfaction surveys demonstrates the role and impact of ethical consciousness.

T. According to the study sample, the recorded value of the correlation coefficient (0.09) indicates a poor association between ethical decision-making and visitor satisfaction evaluations. Therefore, we may reject the fourth secondary hypothesis, which claims a statistically significant moral link between the two, with a confidence score of 95%. This hypothesis derives from the first central hypothesis.

With an F-value of 0.417, considered statistically insignificant, we may conclude that the association between ethical decision-making and guest satisfaction surveys is not statistically significant. Since the two variables are connected, the fourth hypothesis derived from the second fundamental hypothesis must be rejected. There was a discernible effect of (ethical decision-making) on (guest satisfaction surveys), as shown by a measured coefficient of determination value of 0.007%.

Derived from the first core hypothesis, the fifth hypothesis asserts that growing visitor pleasure significantly correlates with moral awareness; nonetheless, it was rejected with a 95% confidence level. According to the results of the study's representative sample, the correlation coefficient was recorded as 0.04, suggesting that the relationship between the two is weak.

The F-value of 0.076 is not statistically significant, suggesting no meaningful relationship between ethical awareness and the dependent variable of increasing visitor enjoyment. The fifth auxiliary hypothesis, a direct result of the second core hypothesis, states that we can disprove the possibility of a link between the two variables. Thus, the value of the coefficient of determination (0.001%) demonstrates the percentage of influence and contribution of (ethical awareness) on (increasing guest enjoyment).

C. A low correlation coefficient value (0.14) indicates that, according to the research sample, there is a weak association between making ethical decisions and increasing visitor pleasure. With a 95% confidence level, we may conclude that the first central and sixth secondary hypotheses, which claim a statistically significant moral link between the two, are false.

The variable representing ethical decision-making does not affect the outcome of interest (raising guest contentment) since the calculated F value was (1.077), which is insignificant. The result is the rejection of the sixth hypothesis, which claims that the two variables are related—the second core

hypothesis. The reported value of the coefficient of determination was 0.018 percent, indicating the amount to which ethical decision-making influenced and contributed to boosting visitor happiness. H. The first primary hypothesis says there is little association between senior management's ethical behavior and enhancing guest pleasure; we can reject this with a 95% confidence level. This is confirmed by the statistically significant correlation coefficient value of 0.08.

The measured value of F was 0.365, which is not statistically significant, indicating that the independent variable (the ethical behavior of senior management) and the dependent variable (the enhancement of visitors' happiness) do not have a meaningful association. This disproves the second central theory, which proposed a causal link between the two variables. The result was the value of the coefficient of determination being recorded. The percentage of influence and input from (the moral behavior of senior management) to (enhancing customer happiness) is (0.006%).

Table (13) shows that the independent variables explain the variation in increasing guest satisfaction, with a coefficient of determination value of 0.006%. Even with a significant discount, the test finds no evidence of a major regression. You can't put a 0.05 on a matter of 2.548. Since it is self-evident that senior management's ethical behavior does not affect the dependent variable on any dimension, we will accept the null hypothesis.

Table (13): Results of testing the hypothesis of the relationship and impact of the ethical behavior of senior management in enhancing guest satisfaction

Interpretation	F- test			Regression coefficient β	Fixed limit a	Coefficient of determination R^2	Pears on correlation coefficient r	Variables	
	Probability value sig.	Tabulation	The calculated one					Approved	The Independent
The existence of a significant correlation and thus accepting the first secondary hypothesis, and accordingly, there is an effect	0.000	4.01	173.802	1.877	-2.75	0.75	0.87	Complaints system	Moral awareness

The existence of a significant correlation and thus accepting the second secondary hypothesis, and accordingly, there is an effect	0.000	4.01	53.433	2.273	-4.41	0.48	0.69	Complaints system	Ethical decision making
There is no significant correlation; therefore, the third secondary hypothesis is rejected, and therefore, there is no effect.	0.985	4.01	0.000	0.007	3.655	0.000	0.002	Guest satisfaction surveys	Moral awareness
There is no significant correlation; therefore, the fourth secondary	0.521	4.01	0.417	0.341	2.575	0.007	0.09	Guest satisfaction surveys	Ethical decision making

hypothesis is rejected, and therefore, there is no effect.									
There is no significant correlation; therefore, the fifth secondary hypothesis is rejected, and therefore, there is no effect.	0.784	4.01	0.076	0.094	3.384	0.001	0.04	Enhance guest satisfaction	Moral awareness
There is no significant correlation; therefore, the sixth secondary hypothesis is rejected, and therefore, there is no effect.	0.304	4.01	1.077	0.531	1.957	0.018	0.14	Enhance guest satisfaction	Ethical decision making
There is no significant	0.548	4.01	0.365	0.26	2.859	0.006	0.08	Enhance guest satisfaction	Ethical behavior of senior

results of testing the hypotheses of correlation and influence between them. Just because a dimension doesn't make it into the final model doesn't imply it doesn't impact improving guests' pleasure. Table (14) shows the findings, and their product is lower than the variables that would show up in the sequential test:

- A. The complaints system's first dimension (173.802) is the most important secondary variable; it's significant (more than the tabular F of 3.16), making it the most influential component of the dependent variable. Because of this, the Stepwise Regression test indicates that there is only one variable in the phenomenon model: the ethical behavior of top management.

Table (14): Results of testing the hypothesis of the association and effect of ethical behavior in enhancing guest satisfaction

Interpretation	F- test			Regression coefficient β	Fixed limit a	Coefficient of determination R^2	Pears on correlation coefficient r	Variables	
	Probability value sig.	Tabulation	The calculated one					Approved	The Independent
The independent dimension that has the most influence on the first dimension of the dependent variable	0.000	3.16	173.80	1.877	- 2.750	0.75	0.87	Complaints system	Moral awareness

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the results of the SPSS V23 program Analysis

By conducting a sequential regression analysis on variables that affect the dimensions of the dependent variable (guest satisfaction), we found that size (ethical awareness) had the most significant impact on the first dimension of the dependent variable (complaints system). This finding highlights the significance of moral cognition in tourism, exemplified by management knowledge and understanding. The flow of information given by visitors allows the Supreme Council to monitor the effect of its activities on other persons, identify concerns, and remedy them. Final Thoughts and Suggestions

A set of conclusions was drawn in the second paragraph based on the evaluation and analysis of the research sample's answers, which were informed by the scientific orientations of the project, as explained in the first paragraph. This process is standard practice in scientific research and always yields some results. The third paragraph, on the other hand, included its suggestions.

1. Findings:

- A. The complaints system is affected by moral awareness, and the two are statistically related.
- B. As a result of a statistically substantial association, the complaints system is affected by ethical decision-making.

T. Guests' happiness surveys do not show any benefit of ethical awareness since there is no statistically significant association between the two.

Th. Since ethical decision-making is not significantly correlated with guest satisfaction surveys, it cannot be said to have any influence.

C. The sample responses examined do not show a statistically significant relationship between moral awareness and improving visitor satisfaction, thereby ruling out any influence.

H. The sample responses examined do not show a statistically significant relationship between making ethical decisions and increasing visitor happiness. Hence, there is no impact.

A closer look at the data revealed that the first independent variable, moral awareness, is the most influential secondary variable on the complaints system's first dimension.

Conclusions

1. The ethical awareness of senior management contributes to the organization's communication with its guests to know their complaints, grievances, and suggestions.
2. The extent of success achieved by a hotel organization depends mainly on the ability and competence of senior management in making the appropriate ethical decision.
3. Sample members confirmed that senior management presents new ideas to develop work automatically and quickly.
4. Th. Making and organizing ethical decisions occurs through careful collection of facts.
5. The senior management of the investigated hotels apologizes to their guests when they fail to provide services and seeks to offer them their suggestions and requirements.
6. The senior management takes care of the guest once they stop calling, makes efforts to restore him, and works to meet all the guests' desires and needs.
7. Senior management uses many means of communication to ask the guest random questions to express his opinions, build a communication relationship with him, and know his desires

Recommendations

1. It is necessary for the administration to know the dissenting opinion and benefit from it to understand ethical positions.
2. Continuing to provide new ideas to develop work automatically and quickly.
3. Make ethical decisions, bear responsibility, apologize when negligent in providing services, and strive to offer them their suggestions and requirements.
4. Continuous communication with guests and providing a complaints box and other means to ensure privacy

5. Continuing to provide high-quality services in various circumstances to gain guest satisfaction.
6. Work to conduct periodic surveys and collect information and data using questionnaires to measure guest satisfaction.
7. The possibility of calling the senior management by phone to ask the guest random questions to express his opinions, build a relationship, and continue communicating with him and knowing his desires.

References

1. Al-Nuaimi, Muhammad Abdel-Al, (2008), Introduction to Statistics with Applications to the SPSS Program, Al-Warraq Publishing and Distribution Foundation.
2. Sheet, Nazal, 2014, "Pricing Policy and Its Impact on Guest Satisfaction," Journal of Management and Economics/University of Basra, Issue 12, Volume 6.
3. Al-Houri, Muthanna Taha, (2004), Legal Relations in the Hospitality Industry, Dar Al-Warraq for Publishing and Distribution, Amman, Jordan.
4. Hassan, Hassan and Al-Ajami, Muhammad, (2010), Educational Administration, Dar Al-Mashra for Publishing and Distribution, Amman, Jordan.
5. Judeh, Mahfouz (2010): Advanced Statistical Analysis, 2nd edition, Wael Publishing House, Amman, Jordan.
6. Ahmed Abdullah Anis, 2016, Marketing Management According to the Perspective of Customer Value, Dar Al-Jinan for Publishing and Distribution, Amman, Jordan.
7. Al-Afandi, Hassan Talal Ahmad, 2018, The Sequential Impact of Green Purchasing Strategies and Green Manufacturing Requirements on Customer Satisfaction: An Exploratory Study of Managers' Opinions in a Group of Furniture Industry Companies in Mosul, Master Thesis in Industrial Management - College of Administration and Economics, University Mosul.
8. Barlan-Espino, A. G. (2017), Operational efficiency and customer satisfaction of restaurants: Basis for business operational enhancement. Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research, vol.5, no.(1), p-p:122-132.
9. Barnes C. M., Gunia, B. C., and Wagner. D. T. (2015), Sleep and moral awareness. Journal of Sleep Research Vol 24, Issue 2, pages 181-188.
10. Bishop, W. H. (2013). The role of ethics in 21st century organizations. Journal of Business Ethics, 118, 635-637. doi:10.1007/s10551-013-1618-1.
11. Daft, R. L. (2015). Organization theory and design. Cengage learning.
12. David De Cremer, David M. Mayer, and Marshall,(2010),Schminke, *Guest Editors' Introduction On Understanding Ethical Behavior and Decision Making: A Behavioral Ethics Approach*,Business Ethics Quarterly 20:1 (January); ISSN 1052-150X.
13. do it right" (5th edn.). Boston, MA: Wiley.
14. Emery ,Emmett (2016), Ethical behavior, Leadership, and Decision Making, _Walden Dissertations and Doctoral Studies.
15. Gibbs, J.C. (2010): Moral development and reality, Beyond the theories of Kohlberg and Hoffman. Boston: Pearson, Allyn and Bacon.

16. Hassanian, Z. M., & Shayan, A. (2017). The mediating effect of ethical climate on religious orientation and ethical behavior. *Nursing Ethics*, 096973301773813.
17. Jones, M.O. "Studying organizational symbolism: what, how, why? Newbury Sage, 1996.
18. Kotler, Philip & Armstrong Gary, (2000), "Marketing an introduction" 5th ed Prentice Hall, Inc, New Jersey, USA.
19. Kotler, Philip & Keller, Kevin Lane, (2006), *Marketing Management*, 12th edition, New Jersey: Pearson.
20. Kotler, Philip (2018), "Marketing Management", 15th edition, New Jersey, U.S.A.
21. Lesley, P & Richard, S, 2005, *The Management of Tourism*, British Library Cataloguing in Publication Data, p. 33.
22. Lin, Z. J., & Zhang, J. (2011). Ethical awareness of Chinese business managers and accountants and their views on the use of off-book accounts. *Advances in Accounting*, incorporating *Advances in Accounting*, incorporating *Advances in International Accounting* 27PP:143–155.
23. Medlike, S, 2003, *Dictionary of travel tourism and Hospitality*, Butterworth – Heinemann is an imprint of Elsevier. UK.
24. Monin, Jean, (2001), *La satisfaction qualité dans les services*, AFNOR, Paris.
25. Olsen, Lervik (2017), *Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty on a Company Level*, Thesis Master of Science in Strategic Marketing Management, Norwegian Business School, Oslo.
26. Qammach M. A., Al-Sharif, N. I. J. (2012). The Impact of Critical Success Factors for E-Learning on Strategic Performance An applied study in a sample of the faculties for the University of Baghdad. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education*, 21, 22.
27. Rest, J. R., 1986, *Moral development: Advances in research and theory*.
28. Starks, R. & Anderson, S. (2012). Moral Behavior of Resident Assistants: A Lived Experience. *The Journal of College and University Students Housing*, 1, 30-47.
29. Sustainability" (13th ed) Pearson, Inc., publishing as Prentice Hall.
30. Trevino, L. & Nelson, K. (2011). "Managing business ethics: Straight talk about how to
31. Vafaei, S. A., Azmoon, I., & Fekete-Farkas, M. (2019). The impact of perceived sustainable marketing policies on green customer satisfaction. *Polish Journal of Management Studies*, 19.
32. Wei, Q, Shi, X, Li, Q, & Chen, G, (2020, January), Enhancing Customer Satisfaction Analysis with a Machine Learning Approach: From a Perspective of Matching Customer Comment and Agent Note. In *Proceedings of the 53rd Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*.
33. Wheelen & Hunger (2012) "Strategic Management And Business Policy Toward Global
34. Yusof, Y., Awang, Z., Jusoff, K., & Ibrahim, Y. (2017). The influence of green practices by non-green hotels on customer satisfaction and loyalty in hotel and tourism industry. *International Journal of Green Economics*, 11(1), 1-14.
35. Zulfiqar, Z., & Shafaat, M. (2015). Green Marketing: Environmental Concern and Customer Satisfaction. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 7(1), 115-126.

Websites:

1. Barakat, Nafez Muhammad, statistical analysis using the statistical program SPSS, Islamic University, 2013. <http://www.site.iugaza.edu.ps/nbarakat-SPSS.pdf>
2. My virtuous brother...my virtuous sister.
3. Peace Be Upon You:
4. This form represents part of the research entitled "Ethical behavior of senior management and its impact on enhancing guest satisfaction / a case study of a sample of managers of first-class hotels in the holy city of Karbala." Your participation in presenting the actual picture is considered to impact producing the research at the required level positively.
5. We ask you to please choose the answer you deem appropriate for each question, knowing that all recorded information will be characterized by confidentiality and scientific integrity and used only for scientific research purposes. We thank you for your kind response.
6. We wish you success in your work

The Researcher

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The first section: data related to the questionnaire respondent

Note: Place a tick (✓) inside the corresponding box

Second: Ethical Behavior of Senior Management

Totally Disagree	Disagree	Not sure	Agree	Totally agree	Paragraphs	N
					Moral Awareness	
					The ability to understand moral situations.	1
					Understand any ethical problem and its causes.	2
					Promoting moral values for employees.	3
					Communicate the ethical task until it is accomplished.	4
					Commitment to moral duty towards others.	5
					Providing new ideas to develop work automatically and quickly.	6
					The administration is keen to know the opinion that differs from its own to benefit	7

Totally Disagree	Disagree	Not sure	agree	Totally agree		
					from it.	
					Ethical Decision Making	
					Gather facts and carefully organize ethical decisions before making them.	8
					Make ethical decisions and take responsibility.	9
					I dare to make ethical decisions effectively.	10
					I am realizing the importance of timing in making decisions.	11
					We are dealing with temptations ethically.	12
					Seeking excuses from others when they make mistakes and confronting moral tasks, no matter how sensitive they are.	13
					It apologizes when it fails to provide services and seeks to offer them by their suggestions and requirements.	14

Third: Guest satisfaction

Totally Disagree	Disagree	Not sure	agree	Totally agree	Paragraphs	N
					Complaints system	
					We are providing continuous means of communication with guests to receive complaints.	15
					We are providing a complaints box and other means to ensure privacy.	16
					Continuously study complaints and listen to them.	17
					We continue providing high-quality services in various circumstances to gain guest satisfaction.	18
					Senior management receives guest inquiries	19

					and responds to them in the shortest possible time.	
					The senior management takes care of the guest once they stop calling, makes efforts to restore him, and works to meet all the guests' desires and needs.	20
Totally Disagree	Disagree	Not sure	agree	Totally agree	Guest satisfaction surveys	
					Work to conduct periodic surveys, collect information and data, and use questionnaires to measure guest satisfaction.	21
					Direct contact with guests to obtain their views on the services provided.	22
					Senior management asks additional questions to measure the intention to repurchase services.	23
					Senior management calls the guest by phone to randomly ask questions to express his opinions, build a relationship, and continue communicating with him and knowing his desires.	24
					A specialized team assumes the role of the guest to learn about the hotel's working method.	25